

Deliverable 7.4
DOCUMENT ON THE
INSTITUTIONALIZATION OF
ONE HEALTH
Workpackage 7

Responsible Partner: ISS

Contributing partners: SVA

DOCUMENT ON THE INSTITUTIONALIZATION OF ONE HEALTH

Terms and definitions:

The **One Health concept** revolves around the awareness that human health is tightly connected to the health of animals and the environment. **Implementation of One Health** is making recourse to the One Health approach or at least part of it. It may or may not be systematic and/or encoded into a definite procedure with roles and responsibility. To date, it is mainly based on the voluntary installment of cross sectoral contacts, mostly based on personal knowledge of the other sector's researcher and officers, and mainly triggered within the scientific domain. **Operationalization** of One Health means bringing the One Health approach out of the boundaries of a concept, and to translate it into a functioning system made up by the interrelation of the three pillars of the One Health: human health, animal health and environmental health. However, operationalization is an abstract domain, which needs to be brought into the programming procedures related with the health protection plans by policy makers to be translated into a functional domain. The latter action is defined as the **Institutionalization** of One Health, i.e. its uptake at the country level.

Introducing the **inter-sectoral glossary**: Translation of terms used in the different sectors to match the significance and introduction of the terms not used/present in all the sectoral dictionaries.

Part I: The context

Translating the One Health concept into an operative scheme has been the goal of dozens of scientific projects and international forums (e.g. the first international One Health forum in Africa Union in 2019 and the One health international forum in Fukuoka, 2022). However, whilst these initiatives have produced evidences, documents and resources to be used for the purpose of installing the One Health approach at the different geographic levels, the experiences that different countries have made in their attempt to include the One Health approach in their own procedures and methodologies, although successful in making progress to integrate the medical and the veterinary and/or food sectors, failed to fully implement all the segments needed for the complete One Health approach to be functioning. In particular, the environmental sector seems to limp on its race to move with the same pace as the other sectors, in terms of technological and cultural development. Certainly, smaller investments have been made on the protection and control of the environment (including the wider meaning of ecosystems, such as the ensemble of the environment and its changes, the organisms standing on the environment as well as their population dynamics) for the mitigation of the impact of zoonoses, which accounts for the different level of advancement of the latter sector. But this is the key to understand one of the missing pieces in the institutionalization of the One Health approach: investments follow the awareness of the importance of this field to complete the bigger picture. In fact, the major obstacle to implement the One Health approach is cultural.

Another aspect to be considered is that the perimeter of the One Health approach is not restricted to the three major pillars: human-animal-environment, but should include other disciplines that are essential when it comes to public health in the broader sense. As a matter of fact, public health protection is not just taking care of the diseases' symptoms, or to attempt to control the vehicles for their spreading to humans, but also should take into consideration the impact that any disease has on the individual and its social context, which in turn impacts the wellbeing of the individuals and the costs sustained by the national health systems and the society. Social sciences as well as economics should indeed be part of the One Health approach in their own right.

All of these considerations should be taken up by the policy makers and translated into actions that are built on the One Health concept and make it an operative system for the public health protection based on the comprehensive contribution of all the mentioned sectors. Such a pathway has been encoded into a guidance document by the WHO, finalized at the mitigation of the impact of the neglected tropical disease (<https://www.who.int/news-room/events/detail/2022/03/16/default-calendar/launch-one-health-approach->

for-action-against-neglected-tropical-diseases-2021-2030) and, although intended to cover a specific niche of the public health, it can be used as a reference for deploying a roadmap for the institutionalization of the One health approach, which is the ultimate goal of this deliverable.

In the following sections, the actions related with the investigations carried out in the framework of the One Health EJP on the institutionalization of the One Health will be reviewed and used as pillars to build the roadmap towards the institutionalization of the One health approach, together with other activities expected to be delivered at a later stage.

Figure 1. Different domains of the One health operationalization: Institutionalization domain is highlighted. Adapted from (<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240042414>)

Part II: Steps Undertaken

Most of the concepts described here come from the SUSTAIN project¹, positioned between social sciences and public health with the aim to understand the political drivers and constrains for institutionalization of the One Health approach across EU member states.

The project was funded by the One Health EJP and started in August 2019 for the duration of three years.

The project's methodology included as first step a literature search on the topic; its results were used to inform specific studies. In particular, quantitative studies of databases and of the results of a survey addressed to institutions working on One Health topics have produced data that have been published in peer reviewed scientific journals [11-16]. In addition, a qualitative study including interviews and observations of the current

¹ The project SUSTAIN (Scientific UnderStanding of the policy process for Transboundary integration And Institutionalization of the One Health across EU member States), granted by the OHEJP, was coordinated by SVA (Sweden) and Roskilde University (Denmark). PI: Olivier Rubin (Roskilde University), Ann Lindberg (SVA).

state of One Health institutionalization at EU and national level, provided insight in the state of the art of the development of the One Health approach.

Inclusion of the environment in the One Health concept

The environmental sector is considered as the weak link in the One health approach. This sector is rarely included in the plans for intersectoral sharing of data when it comes to the management of zoonoses, despite the importance the environment holds as a vehicle and a reservoir of such infectious disease. In turn, the changes affecting the environment also impact the extent of environmental contamination with zoonotic agents and AMR determinants as well as the population dynamics of the pathogens themselves. As a matter of fact, environmental pollution and degradation due to the release of industrial wastes, the loss of biodiversity consequent to the excessive exploitation of lands used for intensive agriculture and animal pasture and the many consequences of climate change, are profoundly changing the planet's ability to resist the anthropic challenges and threatening the overall resilience of the whole ecosystem, resulting in an augmented risk of losing the grip on the spread of established and emerging zoonoses, as has been witnessed by the COVID-19 pandemic.

The European Commission (EC) has set out directives in the attempt to mitigate those effects [1,2]. Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) are in fact the subjects of the EIA Directive (2011/92/EU) and the SEA Directive (2001/42/EC). However, these documents have a strong focus on the environment as the subject of the assessment, while health assessment is only touched upon to a certain extent. This aspect was partially underlined in the amendment of the EIA Directive (2014/52/EU), which specifically notes population and human health as a category for assessment [1,2]. It has to be noted, that the EIA and SEAs Directives mainly focus adverse health effects resulting from negative environmental factors, such as from noise, air quality or temperature, while not considering the population and human health as the subject to be included in the equation beyond environmental health impacts e.g. by considering the effect of environment changes on the diffusion of zoonoses and the remodeling of pathogens' populations.

The World Health Organisation (WHO) has made the attempt to come to a comprehensive definition of health by defining it as a "state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity" [3], supporting the integration of a broad health assessment within EIA/SEAs [4,5].

The analysis of the literature available on the subject, included the mentioned directives, the reports and the research papers published in the grey and white literature. Such an analysis has been complemented with the compared perceptions of practitioners and researchers on the need to include health into EIA/SEA, and allowed to define some recommendations with the aim to inform the decision makers. This outcome could also be a background for the production of official guidelines in order to ensure the consideration of the broader health determinants within environmental assessments. These recommendations include:

1. Additional or enhanced guidance documents,
2. Engagement of health professionals in the environmental sector,
3. Health-related training,
4. Political support.

As a general remark, more research must be conducted. There is a need for unraveling the complexity of integrating health into environmental assessments. Part of this research should include the understanding of how the EIA/SEA Directives have been interpreted by policy makers in different countries. The results would represent a strong tool to fine tune measures to deploy the above recommendations.

In addition, the public health sector should be systematically integrated into the EIA structure in order to make it a mechanism by which the whole society responds to existing local priorities and to issues such as climate change and emerging infectious diseases. Public health input to EIA could indeed enable countries to meet the Directive's objective to reach a high level of health protection.

Cross-sectoral integration in One Health

One Health is of raising interest in the scientific community as witnessed by the increasing number of publications relating to this topic in the literature. The more frequent outbreaks of zoonotic diseases and the COVID-19 pandemic likely have contributed to this.

The critical analysis of the mentioned literature reveals some thematic and disciplinary shortcomings, related to the wider view of the health concept as defined by the WHO [3], in particular concerning the inclusion of environmental themes, social science and economics insights into the One Health policies. One striking finding is that the inter-sectoral collaboration and knowledge sharing should not just be encouraged and implemented, but also broadened to include disciplines related with humanity at a different level than just considering diseases and agents and their ecology at the human-animal-environment interface. As a matter of fact, also the effects that the diseases cause on the human beings and their social context have an impact on the well-being. Interestingly, silos between the disciplines of human medicine, veterinary medicine and environment still persist and the sector of social sciences and economics are far to be sought as part of the One Health circle (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Network of publications on the One Health approach showing the different journals selected for publications. It reflects the effective awareness of One Health in the medical and veterinary sectors and the interrelation (scientific collaboration) between these two sectors. From: One Health. 2020 Dec; 10: 100146.

The understanding of factors that influence human health continues to deepen and to jump ahead of policy. Initiatives such as the Commission on the Social Determinants of Health [6], concepts such as One Health [7] and Planetary Health [8], and emerging scientific research into political [9] and commercial determinants of health [10] clearly show how protecting public health requires to understand the links and the differences between individuals, communities as well as how they interface with their wider physical, social and economic context.

Cross-sectoral integration II: AMR

The WHO, FAO, and WOAHP promote One Health as the guiding frame for national responses to antimicrobial resistance (AMR) (the Tripartite Guide). Investigation of papers related to implementation of 77 AMR National Action Plans (NAPs) in different part of the globe was conducted with the aim to discern regional and income patterns in the integration of the One Health measures depicted in the tripartite guide. The results of such an assessment showed that AMR NAPs almost universally address, in the intention, the three key sectors of One Health namely, human, animal, and environmental health; that NAPs on AMR include One Health measures in the policies related to human health, food production, hygiene, and agriculture.

However, the representation of the more environmental-related issues of aquaculture, waste management, and water governance are low and contra-intuitively more present in NAPs from low-income countries; making the AMR NAPs of low-income and lower-middle-income countries much more congruent with the One Health than those deployed in upper-middle-income and high-income countries.

Case studies I: DANMAP and AFM1

To explore the actual level of institutionalization of One Health, some case studies have been performed in SUSTAIN project. These have looked at the adoption of the One Health principles in the management of specific issue at country level and have been approached by the analysis of the white and grey literature. The first case study was the Danish monitoring and surveillance programme for antimicrobial resistance, DANMAP. The information retrieved in such sources described that DANMAP was developed considering the two approaches: One Health and farm-to-fork, making this plan comprehensive. At the same time the analysis highlighted some shortcomings in terms of environmental aspects.

The scientific literature search conducted in PubMed and Web of Science and the retrieving of the grey literature allowed describing the case as well as the context. From the critical assessment of the literature a strong point emerged on how the environmental component influences the apparent impacts for human and animal health. The second case was related to the management of the occurrence of aflatoxin M1 (AFM1) in milk in dairy-producing ruminants in Italian regions. In the AFM1 case, the identification of the milk metabolite of the carcinogenic mycotoxin aflatoxin B1 shows that dairy products are heavily impacted by changes of the climate as well as by economic drivers.

As a general consideration, the analysis of these two cases reinforced the view that environmental conditions directly influence the onset and diffusion of hazardous factors. Climate change, treatment of soils, water and standards in slaughterhouses as well as at farms can have a great impact on the health of animals, humans and the environment, making it even more clear that the full integration of environment into the One Health circle is a much needed goal to be achieved.

Case study II: One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden

In Sweden, the Public Health Agency, the Veterinary Agency, the Food Agency and the Environmental Protection Agency are all in close geographic proximity to one another. In spite of the search for the largest audience, however, only few interviewees from the Food Agency and the Environmental Protection Agency could be enrolled in the SUSTAIN project's work. The analysis of the replies showed that while collaboration within and across veterinary, public health and food agencies is good, the environment agency still needs to be engaged. The lack of systematic procedures, defining roles and responsibilities for the inter-sectoral connection still cause the asymmetric communication between the different sectors with the environment being the less involved.

Recommendations from the analysis of this case study include to exploit disease outbreak situations to implement interdisciplinary approaches and advocate to policymakers in order to build the pathway to the institutionalization of the One Health. Additionally, experts need to be aware of the different terminologies and practices when collaborating, and thus a shared glossary would also be a tactical advantage. Finally, education could play a central role in raising the next generation of public health scientists and officers (in the broader sense) to be aware of the need to install an One Health framework for better management of events that impact human health. The dissemination of One Health experiences into the school curriculum and as subject of the Summer Schools on One Health as well as the definition of higher educational study courses centered on the One Health message would add to raising awareness of the approach. Lastly, more research should be conducted to enhance understanding of institutional contexts, cross-agency cooperation, and the needs and perceptions of researchers.

Concluding remarks:

The work done in the One Health EJP has allowed to scan the awareness level related to the One Health approach and the practical on-field experiences conducted in some countries where One Health is more deeply rooted. From the wealth of data collected, analyzed and published in white and grey literature it was possible to draw some conclusions that may be regarded as the tiles of the mosaic depicting the institutionalization of One Health. In particular:

- It has been widely shown that the cross sectoral integration, where in place, is mainly restricted to the medical and veterinary sectors. Food sector is also included in the loop although to a lesser extent, while environment is lagging far behind.

- Paradoxically, the operationalization of the One health concept with the interconnection of the human-animal-food-environment sectors is more complete in LMICs than in the industrialized ones, at least with regards to the AMR domain.
- Among the reasons for not including environment systematically are the lack of a One Health policy defining the roles and responsibilities of the different actors and the lack of a common language, which hinders the smooth exchange of the information across the various sectors. The deployment of such a glossary, as the one implemented in the ORION Knowledge Hub catalogue (<https://aginfra.d4science.org/web/orionknowledgehub/catalogue>) would be beneficial in this sense.
- Inclusion of social sciences and economics in the One Health is pivotal and should represent the next cultural investment.
- Lastly, education programs destined to schools and university courses could help in rising a new generation of researcher and public health officials with a more centered target on One Health.

All of the above is expected to boost the demand of One Health policies to institutional and political stakeholders.

Part III: The way forward

All the points raised above represent the backbone for developing a road map for the institutionalization of One Health. In order to complete the picture and to refine the actions part of the practical workflow, the One Health EJP activities include the preparation of a workshop dedicated to the institutionalization of One Health.

This will be organized in June 2023 as a back-to-back event with the stakeholder conference.

The workshop agenda will include the presentation of the work described in this deliverable, and contributions on the many resources and tools delivered by the joint research and the joint integrative projects funded in the framework of the One Health EJP. A presentation on the many training opportunities deployed on One Health will be also part of the workshop's program, eventually follow by a round table involving the major stakeholders that will complete the works with the aim to define the details of the roadmap. The latter will be a milestone of the One Health EJP (Milestone 101 of the ONE HEALTH EJP).

Sources and References

Sources

1. The project SUSTAIN (Scientific UnderStanding of the policy process for Transboundary integration And Institutionalization of the One Health across EU member States) coordinated by SVA- Sweden and Roskilde University-Denmark (PI Olivier Rubin (Roskilde University), Ann Lindberg (SVA)), was the major source of information for this document.
2. Ending the neglect to attain the sustainable development goals. One health: approach for action against neglected tropical diseases 2021-2030 (<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240042414>).

References cited in the text

1. Volume OJ L 124, 25.4.2014. 2014 Environmental Impact Assessment; Brussels, Belgium: 2014. Environmental Impact Assessment, Directive 2014/52/EU.
2. Volume OJ L 26, 28.1.2012. 2012 Environmental Impact Assessment; Brussels, Belgium: 2012. Environmental Impact Assessment, Directive 2011/92/EU.
3. WHO . Health.
4. Nowacki J. The Integration of Health into Environmental Assessments—With a Special Focus on Strategic Environmental Assessment. WHO Regional Office for Europe; Copenhagen, Denmark: 2018.
5. Vohra S., Nowacki J., Martuzzi M. Health Impact Assessments and Health Integration into Environmental Assessments—Developing Further Implementation Strategies. WHO Regional Office for Europe; Bonn, Germany: 2015. Meeting Report of the Expert Meeting.
6. Commission on the Social Determinants of Health . Closing the Gap in a Generation. Health Equity through Action on the Social Determinants of Health. World Health Organization; Geneva, Switzerland:

2008. [(accessed on 5 November 2020)]. Available online: www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-IER-CSDH-08.1
7. Humboldt-Dachroeden S., Rubin O., Sylvester Frid-Nielsen S. The state of One Health research across disciplines and sectors—A bibliometric analysis. *One Health*. 2020;10:100146. doi: 10.1016/j.onehlt.2020.100146.
 8. Whitmee S., Haines A., Beyrer C., Boltz F., Capon A.G., de Souza Dias B.F., Ezeh A., Frumkin H., Gong P., Head P., et al. Safeguarding human health in the Anthropocene epoch: Report of The Rockefeller Foundation-Lancet Commission on planetary health. *Lancet*. 2015;386:1973–2028. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(15)60901-1.
 9. Ottersen O.P., Dasgupta J., Blouin C., Buss P., Chongsuvivatwong V., Frenk J., Fukuda-Parr S., Gawanas B.P., Giacaman R., Gyapong J., et al. The political origins of health inequity: Prospects for change. *Lancet*. 2014;383:630–667. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62407-1.
 10. Mialon M. An overview of the commercial determinants of health. *Glob. Health*. 2020;16:74. doi: 10.1186/s12992-020-00607-x.

References used as background information to lay down this text

11. One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden - Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination. Humboldt-Dachroeden S. *Scand J Public Health*. 2021 Jun 30:14034948211024483. doi: 10.1177/14034948211024483. Online ahead of print. PMID: 34187239 Free article.
12. Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach. Humboldt-Dachroeden S, Mantovani A. *Medicina (Kaunas)*. 2021 Mar 5;57(3):240. doi: 10.3390/medicina57030240. PMID: 33807528 Free PMC article. Review.
13. Attention to the Tripartite's one health measures in national action plans on antimicrobial resistance. Munkholm L, Rubin O, Bækkeskov E, Humboldt-Dachroeden S. *J Public Health Policy*. 2021 Jun;42(2):236-248. doi: 10.1057/s41271-021-00277-y. Epub 2021 Feb 17. PMID: 33597731
14. Lessons from an International Initiative to Set and Share Good Practice on Human Health in Environmental Impact Assessment. Cave B, Pyper R, Fischer-Bonde B, Humboldt-Dachroeden S, Martin-Olmedo P. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021 Feb 3;18(4):1392. doi: 10.3390/ijerph18041392. PMID: 33546244 Free PMC article. Review.
15. The state of One Health research across disciplines and sectors - a bibliometric analysis. Humboldt-Dachroeden S, Rubin O, Sylvester Frid-Nielsen S. *One Health*. 2020 Dec;10:100146. doi: 10.1016/j.onehlt.2020.100146. Epub 2020 Jun 6. PMID: 32835067 Free PMC article. Review.
16. Analysis of Health in Environmental Assessments-A Literature Review and Survey with a Focus on Denmark. Humboldt-Dachroeden S, Fischer-Bonde B, Gulis G. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2019 Nov 18;16(22):4570. doi: 10.3390/ijerph16224570. PMID: 31752239 Free PMC article. Review.